

SOCIAL ANALYSIS OF ISAJON SULTAN'S NOVEL "ALISHER NAVOI"

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Annotation: This article analyzes the interpretation of historical truth in Isajon Sultan's novel "Alisher Navoi". In the process of analysis, the novel "Alisher Navoi" is compared with historical sources.

Keywords: historical truth, artistic texture, artistic image, historical reality, comparative analysis.

The issue of history and fiction is a very interesting, wide-ranging and deep issue in every era. Since the 70s of the 20th century, the interest in the distant past of our nation, the fate and life of historical figures has increased tremendously. Turning historical truth into artistic truth is one of the priorities in literature. Indeed, if history talks about the happening of reality, fiction expresses how it happened. Based on this, it can be said that literature does not simply describe any historical event. At the center of it is the human factor, and the depiction of human feelings and experiences always comes first. Therefore, it should be researched without adding any time and be transmitted to the generations with all the truth. "Artisticity is the main and constant characteristic of art, including the art of words. From very ancient times until now, many scientists have come up with different interpretations and descriptions of artisticity. cannot claim that my interpretation is correct, because the secrets of this phenomenon, which is the blood and soul of art, are countless, and it is found in the literature of every period, in its various directions and currents, in every a national literature and itsin its particular manifestation, it is manifested in a unique way, in a unique scale and level," writes the literary scholar B. Sarimsakov. requires observation in the imagination.

In this way, it will be possible to determine the conceptual foundations of the poetic world of the writer or to understand the scope of thinking more clearly. Because the spiritual and psychological world of literary characters is not always understood in relation to the events of the real world, it is understood in the mind and thoughts. Because an aesthetic look and lyrical warmth are embodied in a certain image, which forms a unique circle of artistic thought that is budding in the artist's constantly moving thinking. Therefore, it is impossible to give it the status of identity with real life. Therefore, artistic truth is not the truth of life, but it is perceived poetically by relying on the text as the beauty created by the harmony of consciousness and the expression of the spiritual vision, by experiencing the creator's microcosm.

A series of large-scale works dedicated to the in-depth artistic analysis of the most glorious moments of our nation's history have been created. Depicting the various stages of our nation's history, the role of DERMAT in the development of the society of the personalities of the talented people who played an important role in the social and spiritual life of our nation, and showing the importance, illuminating the historical reality and personal relationship, as well as clarifying the historical basis of the vital Uzbek romance, the history of our statehood and our national values, constitute the unique national features of Jangan's novels. In particular, novels are an artistic chronicle of our nation's past serves as Many works of art and various films have been created so that we can fully understand the personality of our ancestors. Examples of them are the works dedicated to the life activities of our ancestors such as Alisher Navoi, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Valuable sources were created about the life, literary, scientific and socio-political activities of the great Uzbek poet and thinker, state and public figure Alisher Navoi. In particular, Isajon Sultan's novel "Alisher Navoi" is a proof of our opinion. This novel was one of the great achievements in the field of Navoi studies. "Alisher Navoi" is a work that came into the world with great love, boundless devotion, and joy for the Creator and his creation, the human race, human genius. The reader who gets acquainted with the novel will witness that a significant place is reserved for the historical truth rather than the artistic fabric. Below we will dwell on some places that are compared with the work "Makorim ul-akhloq" by Ghiyaziddin Khondamir, which is considered a reliable historical source about Alisher Navoi's life path. We know from history that the ghazals written by Navoi became popular among the people.

In particular, Maulana Lutfii will also be praised. Maulana Lutfi ul Hazrat, who was unique in the world in the art of words and no one had written more and better poems than him in the Turkish language, one day when he was just growing up and starting to distinguish between good and bad. went to him and asked him: "-By reading a ghazal, let me enjoy new examples of the products of your thinking. He recited a ghazal as follows." Poem: Orazin closes my eyes, every moment is filled with youth. A star and a small sun appear along my length. Mr. Mavlavi, hearing this wonderful ghazal, drowned in a sea of wonder and said to him: came: I swear to God that if it was possible, I would have exchanged my Turkish and Persian ghazals, consisting of ten to twelve thousand verses, for this one ghazal, and the result of this exchange would have been great. I would consider it a success." This incident was reported by Isajon Sultan it is brought as usual. "Lutfiy, who heard the ghazal from head to toe, was delighted - he shook his head with amazement" - Mashallah! If he wants, he will make an ant a counselor to Solomon, if he wants, he will put the kingdom of the world in one ring! - he said, the wrinkles on his broad forehead and

the corners of his eyes spread, and his face took on an extraordinarily bright color. - If he wants, Lutfiy will say the meanings he couldn't understand from this young man's tongue! I used to understand myself as the sun in Turkish, and this boy got the grace I dreamed of until my age at this age. By God, if it were possible, I would exchange my ten to twelve thousand Persian and Turkish verses for this one ghazal, and if Alisherbek agreed to it, I would consider my work a great success! " The seventh chapter of Makarim ul-Akhlaq is devoted to kindness and compassion. In one of the stories in this chapter, Navoi's careless compassion described Alisher Navoi goes back to his private kindergarten after the public prayer, contrary to his custom, and quickly returns. When he asked the reason for this, he answered as follows: "... while I was going to the mosque, I stopped at such and such a place and performed ablution. When I was standing in the congregation, I saw an ant clinging to my shoulder. I was afraid that if it fell off my shoulder and something hurt him and he couldn't find his way home, I would be left behind. That's why after finishing the prayer, I hurriedly went to the place where I had performed ablution and washed him there. I left him in the nest and freed my mind from the fear of being oppressed. "The incident of the ants" is described in Alisher Navoi's novel as the same as the above incident. let's take the conflict of gan, let's take Navoi's life in Samarkand during the reign of Sultan Abusaid in the whirlwind of difficulties, Hossein Boykara's favor in presenting "Khamsa" is all historical fact. completely corresponds to . The value of a work of art and its ability to find readers is determined by how deeply and truthfully the writer reflects the reality of life. We should pay special attention to the analysis and illumination of the complexities of the reality of life in the works of art, how vividly and truthfully the various aspects of the reality are revealed, and how much the means of form served to turn the reality of life into an artistic reality. Every reader in the process of reading the novel feels like falling into that period. A great thinker will be a constant companion on the paths of life. He rejoices together in moments of joy, shares his pain in times of difficulty. The author of the novel who is able to present such feelings to the reader is considered to be able to create a work of a high level. Isajon Sultan's novel "Alisher Navoi" is one of such novels.

If we pay attention to the main idea of the work, Isajon Sultan, unlike the previous artists, names his creative product in 4 parts, after the divans of Alisherbek's "Khazayin ul-Maoni" collection. Alisherbek's depth of mind in his childhood and youth, his sharp judgment, his knowledge and intelligence, surprised even adults, and the creation of his works, which he had in his mind since his youth and wrote them down in his life when he was older, is described in detail. In particular, it is not surprising that his acquaintance with a young man named Babur, the fact that he brought out water, made his country prosperous, and reached its peak became a source of inspiration for him to create the image of Farhad in the future.

Qutb, who has a deep place in my heart, plays an important role in Navoi's growth as a great person, although it is a small character in the work, and it is heartbreaking to hear that Alisherbek, who had black and white eyes, died at the end of his life. was cut off and mourned for a year according to his custom. Kamal Turbati, Abdurahman Jami, Pahlavon Muhammad, Fayzullah Abullais Samarkandi, Ahmad Hajibeks who always supported Navoi during difficulties played an important role in the development of the great talent.

In my opinion, through this beautiful verse, the writer expresses his grievances, that is, Hazrat Nawai also mentions that in the last article of his works "Hayrat ul-Abror" there is a hadith about whether I was able to justify the trust of the teachers. In particular, in my opinion, it is not surprising that our writer also aimed for this. It is as if he expressed his thoughts about the beautiful realization of his dream, which he had buried in the depths of his tongue for many years.

In the beginning of Isajon Sultan's work, the development of the Turkish and Arabic languages, which was mentioned by Alisherbek's teacher Kulohi and was included in the works of Hazrat "Muhokamat ul lug'atayn", is very beautifully described that the Arabic language is the word of the Qur'an, and the Turkish language is the source of poetry. In conclusion, I would like to say that the author can show the charm of beautiful words in the novel "Navoi" as well as in his other novels. He can combine his simplicity and philosophical tones with historical figures, events, and Navoi's poetry.

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